

**Design and Analysis of a Vertical Elastic Vibration
Reduction System for Railway Vehicle Carbodies**

PROJECT REPORT

MECHANICAL VIBRATIONS

**SUBMITTED TO: DR ASIF ISRAR
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Design and Analysis of a Vertical Elastic Vibration Reduction System for Railway Vehicle Carbodies.

Abstract

Aiming at the vertical elastic vibration reduction of a railway vehicle carbody, the traditional technology mainly focuses on the design of modal frequency, the method of increasing damping and the design of dynamic vibration absorber, In this project, a novel vertical elastic vibration reduction method based on the minimum generalized force principle is proposed the vertical elastic vibration of carbody is reduced by adjusting its own parameters weight distribution and stiffness distribution to control the first-order vertical bending. Firstly, to verify the reference paper apply MGFP, a factor called generalized force factor that can determine the level of generalized force (GF) is proposed. By improving theoretical model of a railway vehicle carbody, the traditional uniform cross-section is replaced by truss model, and the influencing factors of modal frequency and modal shape node locations can be investigated.

Introduction:

The vibration level of railway vehicle carbodies significantly impacts passenger comfort. With increased transport speeds, the issue of elastic vibration in carbodies has become more prominent. Lightweight design and structural simplification have reduced the stiffness and damping of carbodies, while prolonged maintenance intervals for wheel re-profiling and rail grinding have exacerbated wheel-rail vibration, increasing elastic vibrations.

Among all elastic vibration modes, the first vertical bending mode is the most critical. Elastic vibration occurs when track-induced external force frequencies coincide with carbody elastic modes. Various technologies have been developed to mitigate these vibrations, including dynamic vibration absorbers (DVA), damping layers, piezoelectric actuators, active/semi-active control systems, and anti-bending bars. For example, anti-bending bars fixed to the carbody underframe have been shown to reduce vibration levels and improve ride comfort. Flexible fluid-filled tanks, designed to mimic passenger damping effects, have also demonstrated significant vibration reduction.

Most existing methods focus on frequency design, damping increase, or dynamic absorption. However, no strategies based on modal shape design have been implemented. Evans highlighted the importance of modal shape node positions but did not propose methods for controlling node locations.

This project introduces a novel vibration reduction strategy using modal shape control based on a truss model. Unlike the uniform cross-section beam model, this model allows for parameter adjustments to control modal shapes and frequencies.

Background Theory:

Traditional Theoretical Dynamic Model Of Railway Vehicle

For a single railway vehicle vertical dynamic model considering carbody elastic vibration, it generally includes one carbody, two bogie frames, four wheelsets, four sets of primary suspension and two sets of secondary suspension. In the model, the flexible carbody is modelled as a UCEB, supported through the secondary suspension by the two bogie frames. The simplified vehicle model considers 7 degrees of freedom (DOFs). The wheelsets are supposed to be closely supported by the rails, which means that no wheel jump happens and vertical movements of the wheelsets are exactly the same as track irregularities. Assuming the carbody as a free-free UCEB, the equation of motion for the elastic carbody is given by:

$$EI \frac{\partial^4 w(x,t)}{\partial x^4} + \mu I \frac{\partial^5 w(x,t)}{\partial x^4 \partial t} + \rho A \frac{\partial^2 w(x,t)}{\partial t^2} = F_{zc1} \delta(x - x_1) + F_{zc2} \delta(x - x_2)$$

where $w(x, t)$ is the vertical displacement of the carbody, EI is the bending stiffness, ρA is the mass/length which is assumed to be constant over the beam length L , μI is the structural damping coefficient, $\delta(x)$ is Dirac function, $Fzci$ is the external load acting at the point xi on the secondary suspension location. Then the displacement response $w(x, t)$ of carbody at location x can be expressed as the superposition of two rigid modes of carbody and FVB mode of carbody

$$w(x, t) = z_c(t) + \left(x - \frac{L}{2}\right) \theta_c(t) + Y_1(x) q_1(t)$$

where $Y_1(x)$ is FVB modal shape and $q_1(t)$ stands for its principal coordinate. For modal shape the i th modal shape $Y_i(x)$ can be expressed as

$$Y_i(x) = E_i U_i(x) = E_i \left[(\cos \beta_i x + \cosh \beta_i x) - \frac{\cos \beta_i L - \cosh \beta_i L}{\sin \beta_i L - \sinh \beta_i L} (\sin \beta_i x + \sinh \beta_i x) \right]$$

For modal frequency ω_i , according to boundary conditions of free-free beam the frequency equation could be obtained

$$\omega_i \approx \frac{(2i+1)\pi^2}{4L^2} \sqrt{\frac{EI}{\rho A}}$$

When only the FVB mode of carbody is considered, i is taken as 1. So far, the processing of the FVB modal frequency and modal shape of carbody is completed. Considering the orthogonality of eigen-functions and the characteristic of Dirac function, a second-order ordinary differential equation considering three DOFs (z_c , θ_c and q_1) of carbody can be obtained by substituting and

integrating along the length of carbody. In addition, after considering 2 bogie frames with 4 DOFs (z_{b1} , θ_{b1} , z_{b2} and θ_{b2}), the vertical vibration equation of the whole vehicle system can be expressed as:

$$\begin{cases} m_c \ddot{z}_c = F_{zc1} + F_{zc2} & \text{(a)} \\ J_c \ddot{\theta}_c = F_{zc1} a_c - F_{zc2} a_c & \text{(b)} \\ \ddot{q}_1 + 2\xi_1 \omega_1 \dot{q}_1 + \omega_1^2 q_1 = F_{zc1} Y_1(x_1) + F_{zc2} Y_1(x_2) & \text{(c)} \\ m_b \ddot{z}_{b1} = F_{zb1} + F_{zb2} - F_{zc1} & \text{(d)} \\ J_b \ddot{\theta}_{b1} = F_{zb1} a_b - F_{zb2} a_b & \text{(e)} \\ m_b \ddot{z}_{b2} = F_{zb3} + F_{zb4} - F_{zc2} & \text{(f)} \\ J_b \ddot{\theta}_{b2} = F_{zb3} a_b - F_{zb4} a_b & \text{(g)} \end{cases}$$

For suspension forces, they can be expressed as:

$$\begin{cases} F_{zc1} = c_{zc} (\dot{z}_{b1} - \dot{z}_{c1}) + k_{zc} (z_{b1} - z_{c1}) \\ F_{zc2} = c_{zc} (\dot{z}_{b2} - \dot{z}_{c2}) + k_{zc} (z_{b2} - z_{c2}) \\ F_{zb1} = c_{zb} (\dot{z}_{w1} - \dot{z}_{b1} - a_b \dot{\theta}_{b1}) + k_{zb} (z_{w1} - z_{b1} - a_b \theta_{b1}) \\ F_{zb2} = c_{zb} (\dot{z}_{w2} - \dot{z}_{b1} + a_b \dot{\theta}_{b1}) + k_{zb} (z_{w2} - z_{b1} + a_b \theta_{b1}) \\ F_{zb3} = c_{zb} (\dot{z}_{w3} - \dot{z}_{b2} - a_b \dot{\theta}_{b2}) + k_{zb} (z_{w3} - z_{b2} - a_b \theta_{b2}) \\ F_{zb4} = c_{zb} (\dot{z}_{w4} - \dot{z}_{b2} + a_b \dot{\theta}_{b2}) + k_{zb} (z_{w4} - z_{b2} + a_b \theta_{b2}) \end{cases}$$

where k_{zc} and c_{zc} are stiffness and damping of secondary suspension respectively, k_{zb} and c_{zb} are primary suspension stiffness and damping respectively, Then the motion equation of vehicle system can be expressed in matrix form as:

$$\mathbf{K} = \begin{bmatrix} 2k_{zc} & 0 & 2k_{zc} Y_1(x_1) & -k_{zc} & -k_{zc} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 2k_{zc} a_c^2 & 0 & -k_{zc} a_c & k_{zc} a_c & 0 & 0 \\ 2k_{zc} Y_1(x_1) & 0 & 2k_{zc} Y_1^2(x_1) + k_q & -k_{zc} Y_1(x_1) & -k_{zc} Y_1(x_1) & 0 & 0 \\ -k_{zc} & -k_{zc} a_c & -k_{zc} Y_1(x_1) & 2k_{zb} + k_{zc} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -k_{zc} & k_{zc} a_c & -k_{zc} Y_1(x_1) & 0 & 2k_{zb} + k_{zc} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 2k_{zb} a_b^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 2k_{zb} a_b^2 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{C} = \begin{bmatrix} 2c_{zc} & 0 & 2c_{zc} Y_1(x_1) & -c_{zc} & -c_{zc} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 2c_{zc} a_c^2 & 0 & -c_{zc} a_c & c_{zc} a_c & 0 & 0 \\ 2c_{zc} Y_1(x_1) & 0 & 2c_{zc} Y_1^2(x_1) + c_q & -c_{zc} Y_1(x_1) & -c_{zc} Y_1(x_1) & 0 & 0 \\ -c_{zc} & -c_{zc} a_c & -c_{zc} Y_1(x_1) & 2c_{zb} + c_{zc} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -c_{zc} & c_{zc} a_c & -c_{zc} Y_1(x_1) & 0 & 2c_{zb} + c_{zc} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 2c_{zb} a_b^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 2c_{zb} a_b^2 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{C} = \begin{bmatrix} 2c_{zc} & 0 & 2c_{zc}Y_1(x_1) & -c_{zc} & -c_{zc} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 2c_{zc}a_c^2 & 0 & -c_{zc}a_c & c_{zc}a_c & 0 & 0 \\ 2c_{zc}Y_1(x_1) & 0 & 2c_{zc}Y_1^2(x_1) + c_q & -c_{zc}Y_1(x_1) & -c_{zc}Y_1(x_1) & 0 & 0 \\ -c_{zc} & -c_{zc}a_c & -c_{zc}Y_1(x_1) & 2c_{zb} + c_{zc} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -c_{zc} & c_{zc}a_c & -c_{zc}Y_1(x_1) & 0 & 2c_{zb} + c_{zc} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 2c_{zb}a_b^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 2c_{zb}a_b^2 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{Q} = c_{zb} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \dot{z}_{w1} + \dot{z}_{w2} \\ \dot{z}_{w3} + \dot{z}_{w4} \\ a_b(\dot{z}_{w1} - \dot{z}_{w2}) \\ a_b(\dot{z}_{w3} - \dot{z}_{w4}) \end{bmatrix} + k_{zb} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ z_{w1} + z_{w2} \\ z_{w3} + z_{w4} \\ a_b(z_{w1} - z_{w2}) \\ a_b(z_{w3} - z_{w4}) \end{bmatrix}$$

The 3 DOFs (z_c , θ_c , q_1) of carbody can be obtained by solving, and then the vibration response of carbody can be calculated by bringing z_c , θ_c , q_1 into equation. Generally, the above model mainly calculates two types of response. One is the frequency response function (FRF) or displacement magnification factor, and the other one is acceleration response analysis under track irregularity which is used for ride quality evaluation. For displacement magnification factor calculation, the harmonic excitation (its amplitude denoted by F) is supposed to be imposed in phase on the four wheelsets at the same time, that is, $z_{w1} = z_{w2} = z_{w3} = z_{w4} = F \cos \omega t$, then bringing z_{w1} , z_{w2} , z_{w3} , z_{w4} into Eq. (11), the FRF at different positions can be obtained by solving:

$$H(x, \omega) = H_{z_c}(\omega) + \left(x - \frac{L}{2}\right) H_{\theta_c}(\omega) + Y(x) H_{q_1}(\omega)$$

And the acceleration FRF is

$$H_a(x, \omega) = -\omega^2 H(x, \omega)$$

And the displacement magnification factor can be expressed as:

$$\tilde{T}(x, \omega) = H(x, \omega) / F$$

For acceleration response analysis under track irregularity, firstly, the power spectral density (PSD) of the track irregularity spectrum is shown

$$S(\Omega) = \frac{A\Omega_c^2}{(\Omega^2 + \Omega_r^2)(\Omega^2 + \Omega_c^2)}$$

where the wavelength is, its unit is rad/m, $\Omega_c = 0.8246$ rad/m, $\Omega_r = 0.0206$ rad/m and $A = 1.080 \times 10^{-6}$ rad/m. As a function of the angular frequency $\omega = v\Omega$, the PSD $G(\omega)$ of the track irregularity can be written as $S(\omega/v)v$, v is the vehicle velocity, then the PSD of track irregularity can be expressed as:

$$G(\omega) = \frac{A\Omega_c^2 v^3}{[\omega^2 + (v\Omega_r)^2] [\omega^2 + (v\Omega_c)^2]}$$

Secondly, when a railway vehicle passes through a track with irregularities, the time difference between different wheelsets passing through the same location needs to be considered, so the track irregularity at different wheelsets can be expressed as:

$$\begin{cases} z_{w1} = \cos \omega \left(t + \frac{a_c + a_b}{v} \right) & \text{(a)} \\ z_{w2} = \cos \omega \left(t + \frac{a_c - a_b}{v} \right) & \text{(b)} \\ z_{w3} = \cos \omega \left(t - \frac{a_c - a_b}{v} \right) & \text{(c)} \\ z_{w4} = \cos \omega \left(t - \frac{a_c + a_b}{v} \right) & \text{(d)} \end{cases}$$

where a_c is half of bogie distance, and a_b is half of wheelbase. By substituting the harmonic excitation with different frequencies, then the FRF of can be calculated accordingly. Ultimately, the root mean square (rms) value of the acceleration at different position x when the vehicle carbody passes through a specific track irregularity can be expressed as:

$$a_{rms}(x) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{\infty} G(\omega) |H_a(\omega, x)|^2 d\omega}$$

A new carbody model based on MGF

From Minimum generalized force principle, the elastic vibration of carbody is mainly related to the modal shape Y_1 and the modal coordinate q_1 . Since Y_1 is a definite value, the elastic vibration is directly related to q_1 . If the force on the right side of the equation about q_1 is written as a general harmonic forces form, the equation of q_1 can be expressed as:

$$\ddot{q}_1 + 2\xi_1 \omega_1 \dot{q}_1 + \omega_1^2 q_1 = Y_1^T \mathbf{f}$$

where \mathbf{f} is the external force vector, if k external forces exists, $\mathbf{f} = [0, \dots, f_1 \sin(\omega t + \varphi_1), \dots, f_k \sin(\omega t + \varphi_k), \dots, 0]$, the length of vector \mathbf{f} is equal to the length of Y_1 .

According to the theory of dynamics, q_1 can be expressed as

$$q_1 = \frac{Y_1^T \mathbf{f}}{\omega_1^2 - \omega^2 + 2j\xi_1 \omega_1 \omega}$$

Since the denominator part is related to the modal parameters, once the dynamic system is determined, the denominator part is a constant value, so q_1 depends on the molecular part, which is the projection of force vector \mathbf{f} on the modal shape Y_1 , that is, the GF gf . It should be noted that GF is related to a certain mode, and GF here is for the FVB mode of carbody. When multiple forces act on carbody, assuming a total of k forces, the gf is expressed as

$$g_f = Y_1^T \mathbf{f} = \sum_{i=1}^k Y_{1i} f_i \sin(\omega t + \varphi_i)$$

As can be seen, q_1 reaches a minimum value if gf is minimized, so the elastic vibration is also the smallest. One extreme example is that the external forces act on the modal shape nodes, since the modal shape values at nodes are 0, the gf is 0, so the mode with $gf=0$ cannot be excited. To make better use of MGFP to study vibration reduction control, a factor called GFF η_α is defined:

$$\eta_\alpha = \max \left| \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{Y_{d,\alpha,i} f_i}{f_{\max}} \sin(\omega t + \varphi_i) \right|$$

where $Y_{d,\alpha}$ is the α th normalized modal shape by displacement, $Y_{d,\alpha} = Y_\alpha / Y_{\alpha,\max}$, the maximum value in $Y_{d,\alpha}$ is 1, f_{\max} is the maximum amplitude in f .

Dynamic model parameters of a metro vehicle.

Item	Value	Unit
L	21	m
$2a_c$	15	m
$2a_b$	2.5	m
m_c	21000	kg
m_b	2000	kg
J_c	0.8e6	kgm ²
J_b	1800	kgm ²
EI	1.54e9	Nm ²
k_{zc}	0.7e6	N/m
k_{zb}	2.4e6	N/m
c_{zc}	80e3	Ns/m
c_{zb}	30e3	Ns/m
ω_1	$2\pi \times 10$	rad/s
ξ_1	0.02	-

Elastic vibration reduction based on MGFP

To study the influence of GF on elastic vibration, a UCEB carbody model is established, and the parameters of model are shown in Table. When only the elastic vibration $w_1(x, t) = Y_1(x)q_1(t)$ of a under-damped ($\xi < 1$) UCEB under harmonic force vector \mathbf{f} is considered, its forced vibration response can be described as

$$q_1(t) = \frac{1}{\omega_{d1}} \int_0^t Q_1(\tau) e^{-\xi_1 \omega_1 (t-\tau)} \sin \omega_{d1} (t - \tau) d\tau = (Y_1^T \mathbf{f}) * \left(\frac{e^{-\xi_1 \omega_1 t} \cdot \sin \omega_{d1} t}{\omega_{d1}} \right)$$

The carbody length is 21 m, its FVB frequency is 10 Hz, and the modal shape can be seen in Fig. the elastic vibration at the carbody center under different GF is analyzed

As UCEB model can only preliminarily study the effect of MGFP on elastic vibration reduction, but it cannot describe how to change the modal shape node positions through the change of carbody parameters, so we use Ansys simulations to describe the carbody modal shape and elastic vibration.

Objectives:

- To minimize the vibration of car body by at least 25% by using trusses and changing material of the carbody.
- To analyze response characteristics, including displacement and acceleration over time.

Literature Review:

1. A novel vertical elastic vibration reduction for railway vehicle carbody based on minimum generalized force principle.

This paper proposes a novel method for reducing vertical elastic vibrations in railway vehicle carbodies by leveraging the Minimum Generalized Force Principle (MGFP). Traditional approaches focus on modal frequency, damping, and dynamic vibration absorbers but neglect modal shape design. Using a variable cross-section Euler–Bernoulli beam (VCEB) model, the study identifies how weight and stiffness distributions influence the first-order vertical bending (FVB) modal shape nodes. By aligning these nodes with carbody–bogie interface positions, vibrations can be minimized. The methodology is validated through theoretical models, simulations, and roller rig tests, showing practical applications for new designs or optimizing carbody mass layouts to enhance passenger comfort.

2. Study on Vibration Reduction Design of Suspended Equipment of High-Speed Railway Vehicles

A detailed rigid-flexible coupled dynamic model of a high-speed railway vehicle which includes car body flexibility, and the excitation of the suspended equipment is established. The vibrations of the car body and the suspension equipment with the proposed design methods are studied. Results show that the elastic vibration of the car body can be decreased effectively by mounting the under-chassis equipment with elastic suspension. Compared with vibration isolation theory, the method based on DVA theory is more effective for suppressing the car body flexible vibration, but it will increase the vibration of the equipment to a certain extent

Methodology:

Initial Modeling On Solidworks:

Firstly, initial model for railway carbody was constructed on Solidworks this design had the initial dimensions and material properties of stainless steel which are to be further adjusted when the improvement is to be introduced,

Initial Model Analysis Verification:

We utilized MATLAB to simulate the behavior of the system under initial condition and initial material specifications. By inputting the system parameters into MATLAB, we plotted the displacement amplitude and force positions. These plots helped us visualize the points at which the value of GFF is zero at different force locations and identify the resonance peaks which are critical points where the system experiences maximum vibration. And we will verify whether our results relate to the reference paper, if so then the initial results are verified.

Design Improvement Modeling And Optimization:

To minimize the vibration amplitude, we introduced Pratt and Warren trusses within the carbody and changed the material to aluminum alloy and observed the maximum deformation and acceleration and observed the percentage improvement within the model

Analysis And Results

After integrating the truss structure into the model, we re-ran the simulations on Ansys to observe the changes in the system's acceleration and displacement. The updated graphs were analyzed to confirm the effectiveness of the truss structure in reducing the vibrations and the improvements were quantified.

Observations And Calculations:

For Initial Model:

Firstly, to verify the model from reference research paper we constructed a model for train body using the following dimensions:

Figure 2:Initial carbody model dimensions

Figure 1:Initial carbody cad model

Initial Model Properties:

Material	Stainless Steel
Width	3050mm
Height	3600
Roof thickness	8mm
End Wall thickness	10mm
Side Walls	10mm
Base	15mm
Length	21 m
Elastic Modulus	$1.93e^{11}$ Pa
Flexural Rigidity	$8.38e^8$ Nm ²
Mass	20272 kg

Theoretical Natural Frequency Initial Case:

Now calculating the values for beta by using relations

$$\beta_i L \approx \frac{(2i+1)\pi}{2}$$

By putting values: L=21, i = 1 we can obtain:

$$\beta_i = 0.2244$$

Similarly, from relation:

$$\beta_i = \frac{\rho A \omega_i^2 L}{EI}$$

$$\omega_i \approx \frac{(2i+1)\pi^2}{4L^2} \sqrt{\frac{EI}{\rho A}}$$

$$\omega_i \approx \frac{(2i+1)\pi^2}{4L^2} \sqrt{\frac{EI}{m}}$$

$$\omega_i \approx \frac{(2i+1)\pi^2}{4L^2} \sqrt{\frac{8.38e8 \text{ Nm}^2}{20272}} \quad (21)$$

$$\omega_i = 41.72 \text{ rad/sec}$$

Comparison with reference model to validate results:

From Matlab script we can obtain graphically the force location and phase difference with displacement the results are obtained as such:

Displacement Vs Force Locations:

Figure 3:displacement vs phase difference

The Matlab plot for response vs GFF proves that the points with zero displacement can be found and the node distances are 4.746 m and 16.433 m respectively, obtained when force is 1000 N and the excitation frequency is equal to the natural frequency, these are the optimum locations for the bogies to be attached for best vibration damping. The GFF can easily provide the nodes with minimum displacement. As a result, verifies our theory.

Displacement Amplitude Vs Phase Difference:

Figure 4:displacement vs force location

Mass Normalized And Displacement Normalized Mode Shapes:

Figure 5: Mass Normalized

The mass normalized and displacement normalized mode shapes also intersect at the same points giving the nodes locations with zero deflection. They will be used to attach the bogies of the carbody.

Initial Frequencies

Tabular Data		
	Mode	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Frequency [Hz]
5	5.	6.4241e-004
6	6.	9.3683e-004
7	7.	6.5259
8	8.	7.2544
9	9.	7.8852
10	10.	9.1196

Figure 6: Initial Frequency

Directional Deformation:

Figure 7:deformation initial

For the initial case we can observe the maximum deformation to be 0.3407 mm as indicated

Frequency Response Initial Case:

Figure 8:frequency response initial

Phase Response Initial:

Figure 9: phase response initial

Acceleration Response Initial:

Directional Acceleration:

Figure 10:directional acceleration

Harmonic Response:

Figure 11:harmonic response

Directional Deformation Y Axis:

Figure 12: Directional Deformation y Axis

Initial Model Static Analysis:

Lateral deflection:

Y-axis deformation:

Von misses

We can thus verify our initial model, since similar results are obtained from reference paper the percentage error is calculated as:

Frequency: 6.64 Hz

Simulation Frequency: 6.53 Hz

Error: 1.66 %

Improved Model Vibration Analysis:

To improve the model, we introduced Pratt and Warren trusses within the carbody and changed the material to Aluminum 6061 alloy T6 and observed the maximum deformation and acceleration and observed the percentage improvement within the model

Design Of Trusses:

Figure 13:truss cad model section view

The Pratt and Warren trusses are used for lateral support as we have kept the base same and have only added trusses to the lateral/side wall of the body. The horizontal members are 200 mm wide, the vertical and diagonal members are 160mm wide and has 10 mm thickness which is the same as the side walls.

Improved Model Static Analysis:

Vertical Deflection:

Vertical Deformation of Improved Design 1

Lateral Deflection:

Lateral Deformation of Improved Design 1

Von Mises Stress:

Von Mises Stress of Improved Design 1

Boundary Conditions:

The train car body is modeled as a beam supported at two points, representing the front and rear bogies. The supports are located at **3 m** and **18 m** from the left end of the beam. The simply supported boundary conditions ensure that each support allows for vertical reaction forces but restricts horizontal movement, while allowing rotation (no moment reactions). These conditions are typical for structural models to simulate load transfer from the car body to the bogies. The applied load consists of the **self-weight of the car body** and the **passenger load**, assumed to be **uniformly distributed** along the entire length of the car body. The reaction forces for bogies are calculated and added to the bogie support locations.

- Fixed Supports at bogie locations.
- Body Self Weight = $9.81 * 11608 \text{ kg} = 113829.48 \text{ N}$
- Passenger Load = $72 \text{ passengers} * 75 \text{ kg} * 9.81 = 52920 \text{ N}$
- Total Load = 166749.48 N
- Pressure Load = $F/A = 166749.48 / 60.4 \text{ m}^2 = 2.76 \text{ kPa}$
- Reaction Forces at each bogie = 83374.74 N

Results and Discussions:

The **standard vertical deflection limit** for train car bodies is typically a fraction of the car body length (L) and is calculated as:

$$\delta_{\text{allowable}} = L/600 \text{ to } L/800.$$

For a car body length of $L = 21,000$ mm the allowable vertical deflection limits are:

$$\delta_{\text{allowable}} = 21,000/600 = \mathbf{35 \text{ mm}}$$
 (conservative limit)

For **Lateral Deflection**:

$$\delta_{\text{allowable}} = 21,000/1000 = \mathbf{21 \text{ mm}}$$
 (conservative limit)

For **Maximum Stress**:

Allowable Stress = $\sigma_{\text{max}} = \mathbf{193 \text{ MPa}}$ for Aluminium Alloy 6061 T6

The **actual vertical deflection** observed was -5.17 mm, which is significantly below even the stricter limit of 26.25 mm. This indicates that the car body has sufficient stiffness to resist vertical deformation under the applied load.

The **actual lateral deflection** observed was -1.977 mm, which is far below even the conservative limit of 21 mm. This ensures excellent stability and ride comfort during operation.

The **actual stress** (13.958 MPa) is significantly lower than the allowable stress (193 MPa), indicating that the material is not overstressed and there is a large safety margin.

The train car body design is well within acceptable limits for vertical deflection, lateral deflection, and stress:

- The **maximum vertical deflection** of -5.17 mm is approximately **5-6 times lower** than the strictest allowable limit (26.25 mm).
- The **maximum lateral deflection** of -1.977 mm is approximately **10 times lower** than the conservative limit (21 mm).
- The **maximum stress** of 13.958 MPa is far below the allowable stress of 143.5 MPa.

Improved model properties:

Material: Aluminum Alloy 6061 T6

$$E = 73e^9 \text{ Pa}$$

$$EI = 1.2546e^9 \text{ Nm}^2$$

Simulation Frequency: 11.692 Hz

Angular Frequency: 73.463 Hz

Improved Model Displacement:

Harmonic Response:

Figure 14: Harmonic response

Amplitude Vs Frequency

Figure 15:amplitude vs frequency improved

Acceleration Vs Frequency:

Figure 16:acceleration vs frequency

Phase Response:

Figure 17:Phase response improved

Improved Modal Deformation:

Figure 18:modal deformation

Analysis And Comparison Of Results:

- 1) Values of displacement, natural frequency and stiffness for the reference, initial and improved model are indicated as such:

Parameters	Reference	Initial model	Improved model
Displacement	0.8mm	0.461mm	0.204mm
Natural frequency	10 Hz	6.52HZ	11.692 HZ
Stiffness	82.9MNm	43.06MNm	62.24MNm

- 2) Comparison of theoretical and experimentally obtained parameters for initial model.

Parameters	Theoretical Initial	Simulation Initial	%Error
Displacement	0.431mm	0.461mm	5.2%
Frequency	6.64 Hz	6.52Hz	1.8%

- 3) Comparison of theoretical and experimentally obtained parameters for improved model

Parameters	Theoretical Improved	Experimental Improved	%Error
Displacement	0.21mm	0.204mm	2.85%
Frequency	12.11 Hz	11.692 HZ	3.45%

Comparing Results:

Mass from center 8m section was reduced from 9468.48 kg to 4043.9 kg with a 57.29 % reduction by using Pratt and Warren trusses and changing material from stainless steel to Aluminium Alloy 6061 T6, hence reducing the cost, we also change window size, number and located them near center region as it highly affected the natural frequency of the system.

The stiffness was improved up to 62.24 % due to the use of trusses and reduction in mass as well. It improved the natural frequency from 6.53 Hz to 11.7 Hz i.e. an improvement of 79.17%. This proves the research paper observation of reducing mass of center section to improve vibrations.

The displacement 0.203 mm to 0.01123 mm, an improvement of 44.7 % and the acceleration improved from 4.095 m/s² to 1.356 m/s² an improvement of 66.8 %. The research paper had an improvement of 46% and we have improved the result even further by an additional 20.8 %.

The research paper focuses on a theoretical and experimental approach to figure out that the reduction in mass of the center section of carbody causes improvement in vibration by increasing

node distance to the value of bogie attachment distance whereas in this report simulation-based validation is done.

In the reference paper to achieve the desired improved vibration there is an excessive reduction in mass at Centre (50%), which is not a preferred choice due to the presence of passengers at centre section and can thus cause structural issues whereas in this project alongside mass we also focused on improving stiffness as well using Pratt and Warren trusses. But to reduce cost, we changed the material which decreased stiffness from 120 MNm to 62MNm keeping the same improvements with a lower cost and as a result improving the design.

Applications:

The introduction of truss structures within systems can significantly reduce mechanical vibrations through their inherent mechanical properties and design flexibility. some key applications and benefits are:

Aerospace Equipment

- **Applications:** Truss structures are used in satellites, spacecraft, and aircraft to reduce vibrations caused by launch, atmospheric turbulence, or operational loads.
- **Mechanism:** Lightweight truss designs distribute stress evenly and minimize deformation, reducing vibration amplitudes that could otherwise compromise sensitive instruments.

Mechanical Systems and Machinery

- **Applications:** Truss-like frames are used in robotic arms, CNC machines, and industrial equipment to reduce vibrational interference during operation.
- **Mechanism:** Trusses provide high stiffness-to-weight ratios, reducing resonance and enhancing precision.

Automotive Industry

- **Applications:** Suspension systems and chassis frameworks often incorporate truss elements to minimize road-induced vibrations.
- **Mechanism:** Trusses absorb and dissipate vibrational energy, ensuring passenger comfort and vehicle durability.

Biomedical Devices

- **Applications:** Truss-inspired designs are employed in prosthetics and medical devices to reduce vibrational impact during use.

- **Mechanism:** The structural flexibility of trusses allows for controlled damping, improving user comfort and device reliability.

Future Recommendations:

Advanced Material Usage:

- Investigate the use of other lightweight materials, such as composites (e.g., carbon fiber-reinforced polymers), which could further enhance stiffness-to-weight ratios and improve performance.

Dynamic Analysis Under Real-World Conditions:

- Test the improved carbody model under real-world operating conditions, including varying speeds, track irregularities, and environmental factors, to validate its performance and durability.

Fatigue And Structural Integrity Study:

- Perform a long-term fatigue analysis of the aluminum-based truss structure to ensure durability and resistance to dynamic loading over an extended operational lifecycle.

Integration with Active Vibration Control Systems:

- Explore the integration of active or semi-active vibration control systems, such as piezoelectric actuators or magnetorheological dampers, to further enhance vibration reduction.

Conclusion:

In this project, a novel vertical elastic vibration reduction method based on the minimum generalized force principle is proposed, the vertical elastic vibration of carbody is reduced by adjusting its weight distribution control the first-order vertical bending. To improve the model, we introduced Pratt and Warren trusses within the carbody and changed the material to aluminum alloy we also changed window size, number and located them near center region as it highly affected the natural frequency of the system.

The stiffness was improved up to 32.84 % due to the use of trusses and reduction in mass as well. It improved the natural frequency from 6.53 Hz to 11.7 Hz an improvement of 79.17%. This proves the research paper observation of reducing mass of center section to improve vibrations.

References

- Study on Vibration Reduction Design of Suspended Equipment of High-Speed Railway Vehicles: <https://shorturl.at/QeI8S>
- A novel vertical elastic vibration reduction for railway vehicle carbody based on minimum generalized force principle: <https://shorturl.at/p3zVS>
- Methods for Reducing Vertical Carbody Vibrations of a Rail Vehicle: <https://shorturl.at/zPWwk>
- Mechanical Vibrations, Sixth Edition in SI Units, by Singiresu S. Rao.

Appendix:

Matlab Script For Mode Shape Visualization:

% Given Parameters

L = 21; % Length of the carbody (m)

EI = 0.017 * 73.8e9; % Bending stiffness (Nm²)

rhoA = 11538 / 21; % Mass per unit length (kg/m)

i = 1; % Mode index (1 for FVB mode)

% Calculate beta_i and omega_i

beta_i = (2 * i + 1) * pi / (2 * L); % beta_i * L ≈ (2*i+1)*pi/2

omega_i = beta_i^2 * sqrt(EI / rhoA); % Modal frequency (rad/s)

% Define x along the length of the carbody

x = linspace(0, L, 1000);

U1 = ((cos(0.224 * x) + cosh(0.224 * x)) - (0.98370634 .* (sin(0.224 * x) + sinh(0.224 * x))));

% Normalize the modal shape

Ui_mass_norm = (sqrt(rhoA * integral(@calU, 0, 21))); % Compute integral of Ui² for normalization

Y1_mass_normalized = U1 / -Ui_mass_norm; % Normalized modal shape

Ui_displacement_norm = 100;

Y1_displacement_normalized = U1 / -Ui_displacement_norm; % Displacement-normalized modal shape

% Plotting results

figure('Position', [100, 100, 1200, 400]); % [left, bottom, width, height];

% Modal shape

plot(x, Y1_mass_normalized, 'LineWidth', 1.5); % Mass-normalized modal shape

hold on;

```

plot(x, Y1_displacement_normalized, '-', 'LineWidth', 1.5); % Displacement-normalized modal
shape

plot(x(226), Y1_displacement_normalized(226), 'ko', 'MarkerSize', 6);

plot(x(784), Y1_displacement_normalized(784), 'ko', 'MarkerSize', 6);

hold off;

xlabel('Position along carbody (m)');

yyaxis left;

ylabel('Modal Shape');

yyaxis right;

ylabel('Modal Shape');

title('Mass-Normalized and Displacement-Normalized FVB Modal Shapes');

legend('Mass-Normalized Modal Shape', 'Displacement-Normalized Modal
Shape', 'Location', 'south');

text(x(1,227), Y1_mass_normalized(227), 'x1 = 4.746')

text(x(1,704), Y1_mass_normalized(784), 'x2 = 16.443')

xlim([0 21])

ylim([-0.02 0.02])

xticks(0:3:21)

yticks(-0.02:0.01:0.02)

grid on;

% Display computed modal frequency

fprintf('Modal frequency for FVB mode (rad/s): %.4f\n', omega_i);

fprintf('Corresponding natural frequency (Hz): %.4f\n', omega_i / (2 * pi));

```

Matlab Script For Force Response and Phase Response

```
% Given Parameters

L = 21;          % Length of the carbody (m)

EI = 0.017 * 73.8e9;    % Bending stiffness (Nm^2)

rhoA = 11538 / 21;    % Mass per unit length (kg/m)

i = 1;          % Mode index (1 for FVB mode)

% Calculate beta_i and omega_i

beta_i = (2 * i + 1) * pi / (2 * L); % beta_i * L ≈ (2*i+1)*pi/2

omega_i = beta_i^2 * sqrt(EI / rhoA); % Modal frequency (rad/s)

% Define x along the length of the carbody

x = linspace(0, L, 1000);

U1 = ((cos(0.224 * x) + cosh(0.224 * x)) - (0.98370634 .* (sin(0.224 * x) + sinh(0.224 * x))));

% Normalize the modal shape

Ui_norm = (sqrt(1000 * integral(@(U) U.^2, 0, L))); % Compute integral of Ui^2 for normalization

Y1 = U1 / Ui_norm; % Normalized modal shape

% Plotting results

figure;

% Display computed modal frequency

fprintf('Modal frequency for FVB mode (rad/s): %.4f\n', omega_i);

fprintf('Corresponding natural frequency (Hz): %.4f\n', omega_i / (2 * pi));

% Compute the modal shape Y_i(x)

% Parameters

mc = 21000;    % Car body mass (kg)

kc = 0.7e6;    % Car body stiffness (N/m)

cc = 80e3;    % Car body damping (Ns/m)
```

```

omega1 = 2 * pi * omega_i; % Natural frequency (rad/s)
xi1 = 0.02; % Damping ratio
Fd = 1000; % Force amplitude (N)
% Derived parameters
omega_d1 = omega1 * sqrt(1 - xi1^2); % Damped natural frequency (rad/s)
time = linspace(0, 1, 1000); % Time vector (s)
% Force location influence (Example 1)
force_locations = linspace(0, L, 1000); % Force positions along the car body
response_center = zeros(size(force_locations)); % Response at center of the car body
GFF_force = zeros(size(force_locations)); % Response at center of the car body
center_position_idx = round((L / 2) / (L / 1000)); % Index for the car body center
for i = 1:length(force_locations)
    % Force location index
    force_location_idx = max(1, min(round(force_locations(i) / (L / 1000)), length(Y1))); %
    Ensure valid index
    % Modal force at the given location
    Q1 = Fd * Y1(force_location_idx);
    % Time-domain response at the car body center
    response = Q1 * Y1(center_position_idx) .* (exp(-xi1 * omega1 * time) .* sin(omega_d1 *
    time)) / omega_d1;
    % Store the maximum response amplitude
    response_center(i) = max(response)*1000; %convert m to mm
    GFF_force(i) = abs((Y1(force_location_idx) * 1000)/(max(Y1) * 1000)); % convert m to mm
    but they cancel out.
end

```

```

% Phase relationship influence (Example 2)
front_force_pos = 3.2; % Position of front force
rear_force_pos = 18; % Position of rear force
phase_diff = linspace(0, 2 * pi, 1000); % Phase difference between forces
response_phase = zeros(size(phase_diff));
GFF_phase = zeros(size(phase_diff));

front_force_idx = max(1, min(round(front_force_pos / (L / 1000)), length(Y1))); % Ensure valid
index
rear_force_idx = max(1, min(round(rear_force_pos / (L / 1000)), length(Y1))); % Ensure valid
index

for i = 1:length(phase_diff)

    % Front and rear forces with phase difference
    Q1_front = Fd * Y1(front_force_idx);
    Q1_rear = Fd * Y1(rear_force_idx) * cos(phase_diff(i));

    % Time-domain response at the car body center
    response = (Q1_front + Q1_rear) * Y1(center_position_idx) * ...
        (exp(-xi1 * omega1 * time) .* sin(omega_d1 * time)) / omega_d1;

    % Store the maximum response amplitude
    response_phase(i) = max(response) * 1000; %convert m to mm

    Q1GG_front = Y1(front_force_idx);
    Q1GG_rear = Y1(rear_force_idx) * cos(phase_diff(i));

    GFF_phase(i) = abs(((Q1GG_front + Q1GG_rear)* 1000)/(max(Y1) * 1000)); % convert m
to mm but they cancel out.
end

```

```

% Plot results

figure;

% Example 1: Influence of force location

subplot(2, 1, 1);

plot(force_locations, response_center, 'LineWidth', 1.5);

hold on;

plot(force_locations, GFF_force, '--', 'LineWidth', 1.5);

plot(x(226), Y1(226), 'ro', 'MarkerSize', 2);

plot(x(784), Y1(784), 'ro', 'MarkerSize', 2);

text(x(1,170), GFF_force(670), 'x1 = 4.746')

text(x(1,690), GFF_force(670), 'x2 = 16.443')

hold off;

xlabel('Force Location (m)');

yyaxis left;

ylabel('Response Amplitude (mm)');

yyaxis right;

ylabel('GFF');

xlim([0 21]);

legend('Response', 'GFF', 'Location', 'north')

title('Displacement Amplitude vs Force Location');

grid on;

% Example 2: Influence of phase relationship

subplot(2, 1, 2);

```

```

plot(rad2deg(phase_diff), response_phase, 'LineWidth', 1.5);
hold on;
plot(rad2deg(phase_diff), GFF_phase, '--', 'LineWidth', 1.5);
hold off;

xlabel('Phase Difference (degrees)');

yyaxis left;
ylabel('Displacement Amplitude (mm)');
yyaxis right;
ylabel('GFF');
xlim([0 360]);
legend('Response','GFF',"Location","north")
title('Displacement vs Phase Difference');
grid on;
function Ui = calU(x)
Ui = ((cos(0.224 * x) + cosh(0.224 * x)) - (0.98370634 .* (sin(0.224 * x) + sinh(0.224 * x))))).^2;
end

```